

PROCESSING AND PROPERTIES OF PZT-FIBERS FOR 1-3 COMPOSITES

H. Scholz, W. Watzka, D. Sporn, L. Seffner*, A. Schönecker*

Fraunhofer-Institut für Silicatforschung, Neunerplatz 2, D-97082 Würzburg, Germany

*Fraunhofer-Institut für Keramische Technologien und Sinterwerkstoffe, Winterbergstr. 28, D-01277 Dresden, Germany

ABSTRACT

Sol-gel derived PZT-fibers were prepared by the melt spinning method. The fiber diameter was adjusted in the range of 5 to 50 μm . As-spun gel fibers were dried, pyrolyzed and sintered in controlled atmospheres applying appropriate temperature/time-schedules. Cracks and pores in the fiber microstructure were eliminated by control of the exothermic organic burnout and PbO-partial pressure control during sintering. The microstructure development of the fibers was analyzed by SEM/EDS. Tensile strengths values of pyrolyzed and sintered monofilaments up to 90 MPa were determined. Ferroelectricity was detected in PZT-grains of monofilaments by means of "in situ" polarization in an atomic force microscope (AFM). Sintered PZT-fiber bundles were uniaxially aligned and infiltrated with an epoxy resin. Permittivity and the poling characteristics of the 1-3 composite were measured.

INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric ceramic/polymer composites have found application in medical ultrasonic imaging transducers [1]. The composite transducers are made of PZT-rods uniaxially embedded in a polymer matrix resulting in a 1-3 connectivity of the involved phases. These 1-3 composites are fabricated by the dice and fill method comprising rods of at least 70 μm in diameter. In order to couple the transducers energy into the desired thickness-mode oscillation, the rod diameter and spacing must be smaller than all relevant wavelengths [2]. Decreasing rod diameters and spacings shift the deleterious lateral resonance oscillations, which are due to Bragg reflections at the periodic array, to frequencies out of the range of the applied thickness-mode oscillation. Frequencies of medical ultrasonic imaging transducers are in the bandwidth of 1 to 30 MHz, depending on the organs to be imaged [3]. Assuming a velocity of sound in human tissue of 1500 m/s, the corresponding wavelength to 30 MHz is 50 μm . Thus, dice and fill is not the appropriate method to fabricate such a fine spatial scale of rods. However, a spatial scale in the range of 10 μm , provided by piezoelectric fiber/polymer composites (Fig. 1), results in a shift of the lateral oscillations to higher frequencies of about 150 MHz. The hydrostatic piezoelectric constant d_{11} increases with decreasing rod diameter and increasing aspect ratio (l/d) [4]. Thus, with fine scaled piezoelectric fibers a broad bandwidth, a higher sensitivity and a piezoelectrically more homogeneous composite transducer results. As a consequence, the transducer size can be minimized.

A further area of interest for piezoelectric fibers is the development of passively vibration damped structural materials. In contrast to active vibrational damping no complex

sensor-actuator feedback loops are required. Piezoelectric fibers with an electrical resistive coating are introduced e.g. in a fiber reinforced composite. Mechanical stress applied on the component is converted by the piezoelectric fiber into electrical energy, which is dissipated to heat by the resistive coating [5,6].

Fig. 1: Schematic of piezoelectric fibers (or rods) embedded in a polymer matrix forming a 1-3 composite

This paper deals with the preparation and characterization of PZT-fibers and 1-3 PZT-fiber/polymer composites, respectively. The essential parameters of pyrolysis and sintering are defined. Ferroelectricity is demonstrated at single fibers and 1-3 composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

PZT-fibers of the composition $\text{Pb}(\text{Zr}_{0.53}\text{Ti}_{0.47})\text{O}_3$ were prepared by melt spinning and subsequent pyrolysis and sintering. The fusible precursor consists of carboxylated and hydrolyzed metal alcoholates [7]. Compositions were varied by an excess of PbO as sintering aid and Nb -substitution to decrease the required electrical field for polarization. The optimum spinning parameters of the metal-organic precursor sol were determined by rheological investigations using a rotational rheometer (Rheolab MC 20, Physika) and a capillary rheometer (HKR 2000, Göttfert). By capillary rheometry the high shear rates ($> 5000 \text{ s}^{-1}$) of the spinning process were simulated. Fibers were spun at approximately 130°C in the multifilament mode by extrusion of the precursor sol through a spinneret with up to 19 orifices. In dependence of the orifice diameter, the sol temperature, the applied pressure and the drawing velocity the gel-fiber diameter was adjusted in the range of 10 to $100 \mu\text{m}$. The as-spun fibers were dried at room temperature for 24 h. Organics were eliminated at slow heating rates (0.8 K/min) up to 300°C in N_2 (99.996 vol-%) in order to prevent fiber damaging exothermic burnout. Up to 600°C the fibers were heated in air. Sintering was performed at 950°C in a closed alumina set-up. PbO volatility was compensated by a PbZrO_3 -powder bed containing 10 wt.% PbO .

TG/DTA-investigations (TAG24, Setaram) and hot-stage microscopy (HT 1300, Leica) revealed the critical temperatures of exothermic effects and fiber shrinkage during pyrolysis, respectively. Crystallization and perovskite formation were investigated by X-ray diffraction (PW 1050/80, Philips). The fiber composition was controlled by chemical analysis (AES/ICP). Microstructural evolution was observed by SEM/EDS (CamScan4, Cambridge Scanning Company Ltd.; kevox-ray detector 3600, Kevex).

Tensile strengths of PZT-monofilaments were determined from measurements of rupture load in a tensiometer (Dynamometer, BYK-Chemie) with a constant crosshead speed of 1.5 mm/min . Sample preparation and measurement were conducted according to the European prestandard for strength determination of ceramic filaments [8].

The ferroelectric properties of PZT-monofilaments were investigated in an atomic force microscope [9]. A fiber surface area of $1000 \text{ nm} \times 1000 \text{ nm}$ is scanned with a Si-cantilever tip carrying $\leq 30 \text{ V}$ voltage, in order to locally polarize domains and grains. The movement

of the tip is detected by an interferometer based on a HeNe-laser. For 1-3 composite characterization PZT-fiber bundles were uniaxially oriented and infiltrated by an epoxy resin. Samples of $3 \times 3 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$ were cut for polarization experiments. Polarization behavior was measured by applying electrical fields up to 3 kV/mm. Ferroelectricity could be demonstrated by measuring the poling characteristics (remanent polarization P_r , saturated polarization P_{sat} , coercive field E_c).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Precursor rheometry

The PZT precursor sol was rheologically characterized at low shear rates in a rotational rheometer and at high shear rates in a capillary rheometer. Applying low shear rates ($\leq 1000 \text{ s}^{-1}$) Newtonian flow behavior of the sol was observed by rotational rheometry. In Fig. 2 the viscosities of a PZT-precursor sol, obtained from capillary rheometer investigations, are shown at different temperatures as a function of the shear rate. Low shear rates result in a strong temperature dependence of the viscosity and in approximately Newtonian behavior. Increasing shear rates ($> 1000 \text{ s}^{-1}$) lead to decreasing viscosities, with less temperature dependence. Considering the range of characteristic shear rates of the spinning process ($\gamma > 5000 \text{ s}^{-1}$) the sol exhibits shear thinning behavior.

Fig. 2: Precursor-sol viscosity at different temperatures in dependence of the shear rate

Microstructure development

Hot-stage microscopy reveals the linear shrinkage of as-spun gel-fibers in dependence of the heating rate and temperature up to 600°C. In Fig. 3 the linear axial shrinkage of stoichiometric $\text{Pb}(\text{Zr}_{0.53}\text{Ti}_{0.47})\text{O}_3$ fibers is depicted for two different heating regimes. The change in the heating rate is due to the organic burnout predominantly occurring below 300°C, as deduced from thermogravimetric data. The shrinking rates confirm these results. Up to 250°C the low heating rates result in higher shrinkage than the higher heating rates (applied $> 300^\circ\text{C}$). Fast heating (2.5 K/min to 300°C and 5 K/min to 600°C) results in a lower total shrinkage (30%) than slow heating (1.25 K/min to 300°C and 2.5 K/min to 600°C), which leads to total shrinkage of 37 %. High heating rates may result in drying and stiffening of the fiber surface in an early stage. The reluctant decomposition of organics in the fiber bulk takes place when shrinkage of the fiber surface is hindered. Thus, a porous bulk is left.

Weight loss and exothermic effects of the organic burnout were analyzed by TG/DTA measurements. Analogous to the temperature range of substantial shrinkage, the maximum weight loss occurs between 200 and 400°C. Fig. 4 shows the DTA plots of as-spun gel fibers in different atmospheres, heated with a constant rate of 5 K/min. Evidently, the oxygen content in the atmosphere is responsible for the exothermic reactions. In N_2 -atmosphere the endothermic decomposition of the organic species is revealed.

Fig. 3: Linear axial shrinkage of as-spun PZT-gel fibers in dependence of the heating rates up to 600°C

Fig. 4: DTA-plots of PZT-gel fibers heat treated with 5 K/min in N_2 , air and O_2

The microstructure development is strongly dependent on the atmosphere and the heating rates of pyrolysis and sintering. Two different types of cracks are observed. Radial cracks extend about 3 μm from the fiber surface into the bulk which are formed at high heating rates in N_2 -atmosphere (Fig. 5a). Internal cracks along the fiber axis, typically S-shaped in cross section (Fig. 5b) are characteristic for O_2 -containing atmospheres. The internal cracks could not be eliminated in air, even at extremely slow heating rates of 0.1 K/min. These cracks can be attributed to the exothermic reaction at 290°C, a self-propagating combustion, which requires low activation energy. Control of this reaction is obtained by reducing the O_2 -partial pressure in the atmosphere. A heating rate of 0.8 K/min in N_2 -atmosphere up to 300°C results in a crack-free microstructure (Fig. 5c). At temperatures exceeding 300°C

elemental Pb can be formed from PbO due to carbothermal reduction. Molten Pb sweats out forming Pb-spheres at the fiber surface. Increasing temperatures lead to evaporation of Pb and reoxidation with subsequent evaporation during sintering, respectively. In order to prevent Pb loss, air atmosphere is applied at temperatures > 300°C.

Crystallization of the perovskite phase in the fiber occurs during pyrolysis to 600°C. X-ray diffraction reveals narrow peaks of crystallized PZT and a small shoulder at the (110),(101) peak, indicating < 5% pyrochlore phase. Pyrochlore is completely eliminated at temperatures exceeding 700°C.

Fig. 5: SEM-micrographs of fractured surfaces of PZT-fibers pyrolyzed at 600°C (a) 5 K/min in N₂-atmosphere (b) 5 K/min in O₂-atmosphere and (c) 0.8 K/min to 300°C in N₂ subsequently 0.8 K/min to 600°C in air

Fig. 6: SEM-micrographs of fractured PZT fibers with 4 wt.% PbO-excess sintered at (a) 1000°C in air (b) 950°C in PbZrO₃(PbO)-bed (c) 950°C in PbZrO₃(PbO)-bed (fiber contains 2.4 wt.% Nb)

Sintering was performed in a closed alumina container using a PbZrO₃(PbO)-powder bed to the fiber stoichiometry. A certain PbO excess has to be maintained, because a Pb-deficiency in stoichiometry is deleterious for the ferroelectric properties of the sintered PZT-body. A further beneficial effect of PbO is the low melting point (T_m = 886°C), providing liquid phase sintering, which supports complete fiber densification. Fig. 6a shows the fracture

surface of a PbO-deficient PZT-fiber sintered at 1000°C in air. The bulk is porous and exhibits no essential grain growth i.e. the average grain size is $< 0.5 \mu\text{m}$. An excess of 4 wt.% PbO in fiber composition and sintering at 950°C in a $\text{PbZrO}_3(\text{PbO})$ -powder bed results in full densification of the microstructure with grain sizes in the range of 2-3 μm (Fig. 6b). Substitution of 2.4 wt.% Pb with Nb leads to mediocre sinterability of the PZT-fibers. Nb shows a grain growth inhibiting effect and as a consequence fiber densification is hindered (Fig. 6c). The niobium substituted fibers exhibit an inhomogeneous morphology especially at the fiber surface. This "rosette" formation may be attributed to a suppression of the nucleation rate and an enhanced crystal growth starting from single nucleation sites, as reported from Nb-doped PZT thin films [10].

Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of PZT fibers are of minor importance compared to structural fibers for reinforcement. Tensile strength values of 76 MPa are reported in the literature for bulk PZT ceramics [11]. Due to low strength and brittleness of PZT filaments, fixing the fibers for tensile strength measurement is complex. Shear stresses and surface grain boundaries acting as notches decrease the reproducibility of measurements. Thus, sintered PZT-fibers of the type depicted in Fig. 6b, exhibit tensile strength values in the range of 2.5 to 90 MPa. The low strength data may be attributed to shear stresses, because SEM analyses of the fractured surfaces revealed no correlation between microstructural defect sizes and strength data.

Ferroelectric properties

Ferroelectric properties of monofilaments were investigated by atomic force microscopy [9]. A locally applied voltage of 30 V results in polarization of single PZT grains. Subsequent scanning with an applied AC field the detector tip yields quantitative polarization signals (1st harmonic) proportional to the remanent polarization of the fiber surface. Fig. 7a shows the topography of a $1 \mu\text{m}^2$ area of a slightly PbO-deficient PZT-fiber (7 μm in diameter) sintered at 900°C/1h. The contrast of white to black denotes the degree of polarization. Thus, only partial polarization (black section) of the considered area was attained. Single domains and single grains can be separately polarized, as depicted in Fig. 7b. The correlation of polarization and the fiber surface morphology may refer to compositional inhomogeneities (Zr/Ti ratio) or crystal growth directions with preferred domain orientations.

Fig. 7: Atomic force micrographs of a slightly PbO deficient PZT-fiber surface a) topography with poled (dark) and unpoled (light) areas b) polarization of a single grain

Effective electrical material data have been measured at 1-3 composites prepared by aligning PZT - fiber bundles infiltrated with epoxy resin. Volume fraction of PZT phase is in the range of 50 to 70 %. Rectangular shaped test samples were prepared from composite bulk material with dimension of 3 mm x 3 mm x 1 mm (fiber direction) and 1-2 mm² electrodes. Dielectric material data were measured with conventional capacity bridge at 1 kHz. Measurements of ferroelectric hysteresis were done with Sawyer - Tower circuit. The results obtained from composites with two different PZT fiber types (4 wt.% PbO excess, sintered in a PbZrO₃(PbO)-powder bed, diameter 10 μm and 30 μm, respectively) are summarized in table 1.

Table 1 : Electrical material data of 1-3 composites with PZT-fibers of different diameters. Remanent polarization was measured after applying 32 kV/cm. The given figures are effective material data describing the composite.

diameter of primary fibers [μm]	relative permittivity ε _r at 1 kHz	loss factor tanδ at 1kHz [10 ⁻⁴]	remanent polarization P _r [μC/cm ²]		coercivity E _c [kV/cm]	
			at 5 Hz	at 50Hz	at 5Hz	at 50 Hz
10	725	200	2.0	2.9	8.7	12.3
30	577	250	2.4	2.6	8.0	10.4

Due to the high amount of structural inhomogeneties pure PZT material data have not been deduced, so far. According to figure 8, the prepared 1-3 composite materials evidently show ferroelectric behavior.

Fig. 8 : Ferroelectric hysteresis loop of 1-3 composite test samples at 5 and 50 Hz. The diameters of primary fibers are 30 μm (a) and 10 μm (b), respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

PZT fibers of Pb(Zr_{0.53}Ti_{0.47})O₃ composition were fabricated by melt spinning of sol-gel derived precursors. Crack-free and dense fibers were obtained by oxygen partial pressure reduction of the pyrolyzing atmosphere and PbO-containing sintering atmosphere, respectively. Ferroelectricity was demonstrated at monofilaments and at 1-3 PZT/polymer composites. PbO-deficient fibers exhibit porous microstructures and inhomogeneous polarization as

revealed from AFM investigations. Fibers containing an excess of 4 wt.% PbO show complete densification at 950°C. Dense fibers of 10 and 30 μm in diameter, respectively, were uniaxially embedded in an epoxy matrix. The 1-3 composites polarized in a 32 kV/cm field yield remanent polarization values up to 2.9 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and a coercive field up to 12.3 kV/cm at 50 Hz, respectively.

Acknowledgements: The authors appreciate the contributions and ideas of Dr. K. Franke (IFW, Dresden, Germany) for AFM fiber polarization and characterization. We thank Ms. M. Roth, R. Jahn and M. Teige from ISC Würzburg for the precursor preparation, fiber spinning and for rheological measurements, respectively. The financial support of the Bavarian State Department for Economics and Traffic is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] W.A. Smith, B.A. Auld, "Modeling 1-3 Composite Piezoelectrics: Thickness-Mode Oscillations", IEEE Transactions on Ultrasonics, Ferroelectrics and Frequency Control, 38 [1] (1991) 40-47
- [2] W.A. Smith, "The role of piezocomposites in ultrasonic transducers", Proc. IEEE Ultrason. Symp. (1989) 755-766
- [3] T.R. Gururaja, "Piezoelectrics for Medical Ultrasonic Imaging", Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull. 73 [5] (1994) 50-55
- [4] Q.M. Zhang, W. Cao, H. Wang, L.E. Cross, "Strain Profile and Piezoelectric Performance of Piezocomposites with 2-2 and 1-3 Connectivities" Proc. IEEE Int.Symp. Appl. Ferroelectr. (1992) 252-254
- [5] G.A. Lesieutre, S. Yarlagadda, S. Yoshikawa, S.K. Kurtz, Q.C. Xu, "Passively Damped Structural Composite Materials Using Resistively Shunted Piezoceramic Fibers", J. Mat. Eng. Perform. 2 [6] (1993) 887-892
- [6] S. Yoshikawa, U. Selvaraj, K.G. Brooks, S.K. Kurtz, "Piezoelectric PZT Tubes and Fibers for Passive Vibrational Damping", Proc. 8th IEEE Int. Symp. Appl. Ferroelectr. (1992) 269-272
- [7] W. Glaubitt, D. Sporn, R. Jahn, "Ceramic fibers from Sol-gel precursors", Proc. Int. Conf. Ceramic Processing Science and Technology, Friedrichshafen, Germany, Sept. 11-14, 1994
- [8] European Prestandard DIN V ENV 1007 part 4, May 1994, "Determination of tensile properties of ceramic filament at ambient temperature", Beuth Verlag GmbH, Berlin (1994)
- [9] K. Franke, J. Besold, W. Haessler, C. Seegebarth, "Modification and detection of domains on ferroelectric PZT films by scanning force microscopy", Surface Science Letters 302 (1994) L283-L288
- [10] A.H. Carim, B.A. Tuttle, D.H. Doughty, S.L. Martinez, "Microstructure of Solution-Processed Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT) Thin Films", J. Am. Ceram. Soc. 74 [6] 1455-58
- [11] S. Yoshikawa, U. Selvaraj, P. Moses, Q. Jiang, T. Shrout, "Pb(Zr,Ti)O₃ [PZT] Fibers--Fabrication and Properties", Ferroelectrics 154 (1994) 325-30